

Unlocking cardiographic-based biometric potential: Insights from feature selection

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Materials and methods

The features used in this study, including their domains, units, and descriptions, are summarized in Table A1. This table outlines the comprehensive set of extracted features from ECG and ICG signals, providing detailed references for their derivation and relevance.

TABLE A1. Features extracted from ECG and ICG signals with their domains, units, descriptions, and references, categorized by temporal, amplitude, slope, and morphological characteristics.

Feature		Domain	Unit	Description	Referece(s)
ECG	RR_int	Temporal	ms	Heart rate	Pale et al., (2021)
	QRS_int			Duration of depolarization of ventricle	
	T_int			Duration of repolarization of ventricle	Israel et al., (2005); Tan & Perkowski, (2016)
	QT_int			Duration of depolarisation and repolarisation of ventricle	Patro et al., (2022)
	ST_int			Duration between end of depolarisation until the end of repolarisation of ventricle	Israel et al., (2005); Patro et al., (2022)
	RQ_amp	Amplitude	mV	Amplitude difference between R and Q point in QRS complex	Wang et al., (2007); Patro et al., (2022)
	RS_amp			Amplitude difference between R and Q point in QRS complex	Wang et al., (2007); Patro et al., (2022)
	RT_amp			Amplitude difference between R peak and T peak	Pal & Singh, (2018)

Feature		Domain	Unit	Description	Referece(s)
	TT1_amp			Amplitude difference between peak and the begining of T wave	Wang et al., (2007); Tan & Perkowski (2016)
	TT2_amp			Amplitude difference between peak and the endpoint of T wave	
	QR_slope	Slope	V/s	Slope of QR segment	Patro et al., (2022)
	RS_slope			Slope of SR segment	
	TT1_slope			Slope between the beginning and the peak of T wave	Inspired by Patro et al., (2022)
	TT2_slope			Slope between the peak and the endpoint of T wave	
	ECGQRScres _t	Morphologica _l	/	Crest factor of QRS complex	Inspired by Antić et al., (2020);
	ECGTcrest			Crest factor of T wave	Antić et al., (2020);
ICG	BX_int	Temporal	ms	Left Ventricular Ejection Time (LVET)	Pale et al. (2021)
	CB_amp	Amplitude	mV	Amplitude difference between C peak and B point	
	CX_amp			Amplitude difference between C point and X point	Antić et al., (2020)
	CB_slope	Slope	V/s	Slope of BC segment	Inspired by Patro et al., (2022) and Pale et al., (2021)
	CX_slope			Slope of CX segment	
	ICGerest	Morphologica _l	/	Crest factor of BCX complex	Antić et al., (2020)
ECG\ICG	RC_int	Temporal	ms	Duration between peak of electrical and peak of mechanical activity	Inspired by Patro et al., (2022) and Antić et al., (2020)
	QX_int			Duration between onset of depolarization until the end of mechanical activity of ventricles	
	QB_int			Duration between onset of depolarization until the beginning of mechanical activity of ventricles	
	SX_int			Duration between end of depolarization until the end of mechanical activity of ventricles	
	SB_int			Duration between the end of depolarization until the beginning of the mechanical activity of the ventricles	
	BT_int			Duration between the peak of repolarization until the beginning of mechanical activity until of ventricles	

Feature		Domain	Unit	Description	Referece(s)
	TX_int			Duration between the peak of repolarization until the end of mechanical activity of ventricles	

Results

The cross-correlation between all features, calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient, is presented in form of heatmap in Fig. A1.

Figure A1. The heatmap indicating Pearson cross-correlation for all features

The hierarchical clustering dendrogram shows the grouping of features based on their correlation distances, revealing 5 distinct clusters at varying linkage distances. The dendrogram is presented in Fig. A2.

Figure A2. The hierarchical clustering of features using Ward's linkage

The detailed table containing Pearson cross-correlation coefficient for highly correlated pairs of features, which is 0.7 in absolute value for this study, is presented in TABLE A2. It is interesting to notice that all pairs in the table exhibit positive correlation.

TABLE A2. Pearson cross-correlation coefficients ($|r| \geq 0.7$) for highly correlated pairs of features, highlighting strong linear relationships between the respective feature pairs.

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation
QX_int	SX_int	0.98
RQ_amp	RT_amp	0.96
TT2_amp	TT2_slope	0.95
BX_int	SX_int	0.95
RS_amp	RS_slope	0.94
BX_int	QX_int	0.94
SX_int	TX_int	0.93
RQ_amp	QR_slope	0.92
QT_int	ST_int	0.92
QX_int	TX_int	0.91

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation
TT1_amp	TT2_amp	0.9
RS_amp	RQ_amp	0.89
TT1_amp	TT1_slope	0.88
BX_int	TX_int	0.88
TT1_amp	TT2_slope	0.87
RT_amp	QR_slope	0.87
CX_amp	CB_slope	0.86
RS_amp	RT_amp	0.86
CB_amp	CX_amp	0.85
QB_int	SB_int	0.83
TT2_amp	TT1_slope	0.82
RS_amp	QR_slope	0.82
QRS_int	ECGQRScrest	0.81
TT1_slope	TT2_slope	0.79
RQ_amp	RS_slope	0.77
RC_int2	SB_int	0.77
CB_amp	CB_slope	0.76
QR_slope	RS_slope	0.74
RT_amp	RS_slope	0.74
CX_amp	CX_slope	0.73
ST_int	BT_int	0.71

The results of the statistical tests comparing whether there are significant differences between features extracted during baseline recordings and segments with induced anger are presented in TABLE A3. The table includes the feature names, the type of test performed, the raw p-values, and the adjusted p-values (corrected for multiple comparisons). Features that exhibit significant changes between the two conditions are highlighted in bold for clarity. This analysis provides valuable insight into which features are most influenced by emotional states, helping to understand their potential impact on the identification process. Based on the TABLE A3, it is identified that 13 features significantly change with the change in emotional state of the subject.

TABLE A3. The results of statistical analysis investigating difference between features extracted from baseline and anger-induced segment. Beside name of the feature, appropriate statistical test is indicated with p -value and adjusted p -value

Column	Test	p -value	Adjusted p -value
RR	Mann-Whitney U	<0.001	<0.001
RC_int		<0.001	<0.001
ICGcrest		<0.001	<0.001
TT1_slope		<0.001	<0.001
CB_amp		<0.001	<0.001
TT1_amp		<0.001	<0.001
CB_slope		<0.001	<0.001
ST_int		<0.001	<0.001
QT_int		<0.001	<0.001
T_int		<0.001	<0.001
BT_int		<0.001	<0.001
QX_int		0.001	0.029
BX_int		0.001	0.029
SX_int		0.007	0.203
CX_slope		0.021	0.609
SB_int		0.386	1.000
TX_int		0.797	1.000
QB_int		0.370	1.000
QRS_int		0.991	1.000
ECGQRScrest		0.525	1.000
TT2_slope		0.132	1.000
RS_slope		0.150	1.000
QR_slope		0.532	1.000
TT2_amp		0.052	1.000
RT_amp		0.772	1.000
RQ_amp		0.388	1.000
RS_amp		0.126	1.000
CX_amp		0.072	1.000
ECGTcrest		0.535	1.000

The observation of highly correlated feature pairs displaying opposing statistical significance when comparing baseline and anger segments is summarized in TABLE A4. This table presents the variable names, Pearson cross-correlation coefficients, significance status, and adjusted p -values for each variable, emphasizing the inconsistencies in significance outcomes despite strong correlations between the features.

TABLE A4. Highly correlated feature pairs with opposite statistical significance when comparing baseline and anger segments. The table includes variable names, Pearson correlation coefficients, significance status, and adjusted p-values for both variables, highlighting inconsistencies in statistical significance despite strong correlations.

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation coefficient	Significance variable 1	Significance variable 2	Adj <i>p</i> -value variable 1	Adj <i>p</i> -value variable 2
QX_int	SX_int	0.98	True	False	0.029	0.203
BX_int	SX_int	0.95	True	False	0.029	0.203
QX_int	TX_int	0.91	True	False	0.029	1.0
TT1_amp	TT2_amp	0.9	True	False	< 0.001	1.0
BX_int	TX_int	0.88	True	False	0.029	1.0
TT1_amp	TT2_slope	0.87	True	False	< 0.001	1.0
CX_amp	CB_slope	0.86	False	True	1.0	< 0.001
CB_amp	CX_amp	0.85	True	False	< 0.001	1.0
TT2_amp	TT1_slope	0.82	False	True	1.0	< 0.001
TT1_slope	TT2_slope	0.79	True	False	< 0.001	1.0
RC_int2	SB_int	0.77	True	False	< 0.001	1.0

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